

Refractive index study on mixing properties of some binary liquid mixtures

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Manuscript received 12 July 2005, revised 24 March 2006, accepted 4 April 2006

Abstract : Density and refractive index have been experimentally determined for binary liquid mixtures of methyl acetate, ethyl acetate, propyl acetate and butyl acetate with *n*-butanol, iso-butanol at 303.15 K, 308.15 K and 313.15 K. A comparative study of Lorentz-Lorenz (L-L), Weiner (W), Heller (H), Gladstone-Dale (G-D), Arago-Biot (A-B), Eykman (Eyk), Newton (Nw), Eyring-John (E-J), Oster (Os) relations for determining the refractive index of a liquid has been carried out to test their validity for the eight binaries over the entire mole fraction range of methyl acetate, ethyl acetate, propyl acetate and butyl acetate at 303.15 K, 308.15 K, 313.15 K. Comparison of various mixing rules has been expressed in terms of average percentage deviation. From the experimentally measured values, refractive index deviations at different temperatures have been computed and fitted to the Redlich-Kister polynomial equation to derive the binary coefficients and standard deviations.

Keywords : Refractive index, liquid mixtures, solute-solvent interactions.

Refractive index and density measurements of binary liquid mixtures is essential for determination of composition of binary liquid mixtures usually for non ideal mixtures where direct experimental measurements are performed over the entire composition range. Most empirical approach for calculating the excess properties is an attempt to explain non ideality in terms of specific and non specific intermolecular interaction. The most widely used rules for predictivity refractivity in case of binary liquid mixtures are Arago-Biot¹, Gladstone-Dale², Lorentz-Lorenz^{3,4}, Eykman⁵, Weiner⁶, Heller⁷, Newton⁸, Oster⁹ and Eyring-John¹⁰. Many authors¹¹⁻¹⁹ has applied their properties to study the structures, solvent-solute interactions and the solvation behaviour in binary liquid mixtures.

Results and discussion

Refraction arises from the presence of extra nuclear electron of atom tend to follow the oscillations of the electro-magnetic field associated with light. As per Clausius-Mosotti equation, at a particular frequency of light $[R] = 4\pi N\alpha/3$, while $N =$ Avogadro's number and α is electronic polarizability of the molecules of medium. Polarizability of medium is sum of polarizabilities of constituent atoms. Refractive index depends on the wavelength of light.

The experimental refractive indices of esters with alcohols are presented in Tables 1 and 2 and the data have been used to evaluate refractive index deviations,

$$n^E = n_m - \sum x_i n_i \quad (1)$$

where x_i and n_i represent the mole fraction and the refractive index of the i -th component respectively and n_m is the refractive index of the binary liquid mixture.

The refractive index deviations were fitted with Redlich-Kister²⁰ polynomial equation of the form

$$n^E = x_1 x_2 \sum_{i=0}^k A_i (x_1 - x_2)^i \quad (2)$$

where k is the number of estimated parameters and A_i are the polynomial coefficients evaluated by fitting the equation to the experimental result with a least squares regression method. The standard deviations σ were calculated using the expression,

$$\sigma = [\sum (n_{\text{exp}} - n_{\text{cal}})^2 / (N - K)]^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

where N is the number of measurements. The values of coefficients A_i and the standard deviations are presented in Table 3.

Figs. 1 and 2 represents the values of refractive index deviation of esters with alcohols varying with the mole fraction of the first component for the binary mixtures at 303.15 K. n^E values for all systems are negative over the complete mole fraction range indicative of strong intermolecular interactions related to decrease in molar volume and negative enthalpy change on mixing.

Table I. Refractive index of binary systems of esters with alcohols at 303.15 K

Methyl acetate + <i>n</i> -butanol			Methyl acetate + iso-butanol			Ethyl acetate + <i>n</i> -butanol		
X_1	n_{exp}	ρ (g cm ⁻³)	X_1	n_{exp}	ρ (g cm ⁻³)	X_1	n_{exp}	r (g cm ⁻³)
0.0000	1.3999	0.8052	0.0000	1.3951	0.7982	0.0000	1.3999	0.8052
0.0569	1.3969	0.8112	0.0577	1.3924	0.8028	0.0468	1.3973	0.8102
0.1131	1.3942	0.8177	0.1139	1.3900	0.8084	0.0948	1.3953	0.8124
0.2230	1.3908	0.8272	0.2245	1.3862	0.8201	0.1893	1.3918	0.8199
0.3297	1.3871	0.8360	0.3317	1.3817	0.8313	0.2859	1.3888	0.8288
0.4335	1.3827	0.8366	0.4376	1.3774	0.8427	0.3838	1.3849	0.8372
0.5344	1.3769	0.8651	0.5385	1.3714	0.8570	0.4830	1.3791	0.8463
0.6326	1.3719	0.8755	0.6347	1.3699	0.8696	0.5836	1.3746	0.8542
0.7281	1.3694	0.8847	0.7299	1.3689	0.8829	0.6855	1.3726	0.8647
0.8211	1.3679	0.8972	0.8224	1.3685	0.8956	0.7889	1.3713	0.8729
0.9117	1.3674	0.9124	0.9124	1.3680	0.9113	0.8937	1.3706	0.8827
0.9561	1.3671	0.9222	0.9565	1.3675	0.9183	0.9466	1.3704	0.8876
1.0000	1.3670	0.9277	1.0000	1.3670	0.9277	0.0000	1.3703	0.8939
Ethyl acetate + iso-butanol			Propyl acetate + <i>n</i> -butanol			Propyl acetate + iso-butanol		
X_1	n_{exp}	ρ (g cm ⁻³)	X_1	n_{exp}	ρ (g cm ⁻³)	X_1	n_{exp}	ρ (g cm ⁻³)
0.0000	1.3951	0.7982	0.0000	1.3999	0.8052	0.0000	1.3951	0.7982
0.0472	1.3928	0.8020	0.0402	1.3979	0.8095	0.0405	1.3933	0.8015
0.0948	1.3910	0.8051	0.0813	1.3957	0.8117	0.0820	1.3926	0.8047
0.1907	1.3877	0.8144	0.1661	1.3929	0.8190	0.1673	1.3912	0.8127
0.2877	1.3851	0.8230	0.2546	1.3911	0.8263	0.2563	1.3908	0.8211
0.3877	1.3844	0.8313	0.3469	1.3881	0.8342	0.3507	1.3899	0.8293
0.4872	1.3833	0.8598	0.4435	1.3873	0.8423	0.4476	1.3892	0.8373
0.5858	1.3821	0.8505	0.5445	1.3863	0.8501	0.5467	1.3886	0.8464
0.6875	1.3807	0.8612	0.6503	1.3859	0.8586	0.6523	1.3876	0.8559
0.7905	1.3791	0.8712	0.7612	1.3846	0.8665	0.7628	1.3862	0.8647
0.8946	1.3769	0.8824	0.8777	1.3831	0.8749	0.8786	1.3846	0.8742
0.9471	1.3731	0.8871	0.9381	1.3822	0.8790	0.9385	1.3822	0.8787
1.0000	1.3703	0.8939	1.0000	1.3816	0.8834	1.0000	1.3816	0.8834
Butyl acetate + <i>n</i> -butanol			Butyl acetate + iso-butanol					
X_1	n_{exp}	ρ (g cm ⁻³)	X_1	n_{exp}	ρ (g cm ⁻³)			
0.0000	1.3999	0.8052	0.0000	1.3951	0.7982			
0.0352	1.3983	0.8087	0.0355	1.3946	0.8008			
0.0715	1.3964	0.8109	0.0721	1.3938	0.8042			
0.1478	1.3953	0.8179	0.1490	1.3929	0.8110			
0.2293	1.3945	0.8238	0.2308	1.3918	0.8192			
0.3164	1.3936	0.8312	0.3200	1.3909	0.8272			
0.4098	1.3929	0.8384	0.4138	1.3906	0.8348			
0.5101	1.3921	0.8460	0.5124	1.3902	0.8422			
0.6183	1.3915	0.8525	0.6204	1.3899	0.8506			
0.7353	1.3906	0.8602	0.7370	1.3897	0.8582			
0.8320	1.3899	0.8671	0.8331	1.3895	0.8660			
0.9395	1.3895	0.8704	0.9301	1.3893	0.8703			
1.0000	1.3890	0.8732	1.0000	1.3990	0.8732			

Following nine equations are used for quantitative determination of refractive indices of binary solutions.

Arago-Biot (A-B) :

$$n = n_1\phi_1 + n_2\phi_2 \tag{4}$$

Dale-Gladstone (D-G) :

$$n - 1 = (n_1 - 1)\phi_1 + (n_2 - 1)\phi_2 \tag{5}$$

Lorentz-Lorenz (L-L) :

$$\frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 2} = \left(\frac{n_1^2 - 1}{n_1^2 + 2} \right) \phi_1 + \left(\frac{n_2^2 - 1}{n_2^2 + 2} \right) \phi_2 \tag{6}$$

Eykman (Eyk) :

$$\frac{n^2 - 1}{n + 0.4} = \left(\frac{n_1^2 - 1}{n_1 + 0.4} \right) \phi_1 + \left(\frac{n_2^2 - 1}{n_2 + 20.4} \right) \phi_2 \tag{7}$$

Weiner (W) :

$$\frac{n^2 - n_1^2}{n^2 + 2n_2^2} = \left[\frac{n_2^2 - n_1^2}{n_2^2 + 2n_1^2} \right] \phi_2 \tag{8}$$

Heller (H) :

$$\frac{n - n_1}{n_1'} = \frac{3}{2} \left[\frac{(n_2/n_1)^2 - 1}{(n_2/n_1)^2 + 2} \right] \phi_2 \tag{9}$$

Newton (Nw)

$$n^2 - 1 = (n_1^2 - 1) \phi_1 + (n_2^2 - 1) \phi_2 \quad (10)$$

Oster (Os)

$$\frac{(n^2 - 1)(2n^2 + 1)}{n^2} = \frac{(n_1^2 - 1)(2n_1^2 + 1)}{n_1^2} \phi_1 + \frac{(n_2^2 - 1)(2n_2^2 + 1)}{n_2^2} \phi_2 \quad (11)$$

Eyring and John (E-J) :

$$n = n_1 \phi_1^{1/2} + 2(n_1 n_2)^{1/2} \phi_1 \phi_2 + n_2 \phi_2^2 \quad (12)$$

In all these equations, here n = refractive index of mixture, n_1 = refractive index of pure component-1, n_2 = refractive index of pure component-2, ϕ_1 = volume fraction-1, ϕ_2 = volume fraction-2,

where $\phi_1 = \frac{x_1 v_1}{\sum x_i v_i}$ and $\phi_2 = \frac{x_2 v_2}{\sum x_i v_i}$

Here, x is the mole fraction and v is the molar volume of component.

Table 2. Refractive index and densities of methyl acetate (x_1) + n -butanol (x_2) at 303 15, 308 15 and 313 15 K

x_1	303 15 K		308 15 K		313 15 K	
	n_{exp}	ρ (g cm ⁻³)	n_{exp}	ρ (g cm ⁻³)	n_{exp}	ρ (g cm ⁻³)
0.0000	1.3999	0.8052	1.3977	0.8032	1.3046	0.7964
0.0569	1.3969	0.8112	1.3965	0.8100	1.3934	0.8010
0.1131	1.3942	0.8177	1.3948	0.8142	1.3920	0.8084
0.2230	1.3908	0.8272	1.3924	0.8154	1.3904	0.8143
0.3297	1.3871	0.8361	1.3900	0.8183	1.3890	0.8168
0.4335	1.3827	0.8468	1.3880	0.8232	1.3873	0.8206
0.5344	1.3769	0.8651	1.3845	0.8264	1.3840	0.8232
0.6316	1.3719	0.8755	1.3815	0.8286	1.3810	0.8263
0.7281	1.3694	0.8847	1.3789	0.8346	1.3780	0.8289
0.8211	1.3679	0.8972	1.3765	0.8431	1.3760	0.8321
0.9117	1.3674	0.9124	1.3745	0.8543	1.3742	0.8366
0.9561	1.3671	0.9222	1.3700	0.8665	1.3695	0.8468
1.0000	1.3670	0.9277	1.3660	0.8881	1.3651	0.8501

A close perusal of Table 4 reveals that for all binary mixtures these mixing rules show a good agreement.

In all selected systems, refractive index values predicted by Weiner has shown excellent agreement with experimental values followed by Newton and Oster relation, which gives fairly good results, where deviation from theoretical values are more in case of Heller relation. Weiner relation has performed well in case of all binary systems because the variation and deviation with concentration is monotonic without a maximum and with a change in sign. The deviations are within both positive and negative values in all the nine rules so studied. In general for binary systems the devi-

ations are found to be negative where dispersion and dipolar interactions are operating and deviations are found positive where charge transfer and hydrogen bonding interactions lead to formation of complex species between the molecules. Some of the factors which may contribute to these deviations are (i) Breaking of hydrogen bonding between alcohol molecules, (ii) Interstitial accommodation of one component into another component, (iii) Possible hydrogen bonding between ester and alcohol molecules and (iv) Interaction between unlike molecules. It is suggested that deviation of theoretical values from experimental values can be reduced if excess volumes is taken into consideration. So the small negative deviations can be accounted for the volume deviation without consideration that there is no change in molecular polarizability on mixing of the component.

Table 3. Parameters A_i and standard deviations σ for binary liquid mixtures at 303 15 K, 308 15 K and 313 15 K for n^E

T (K)	Methyl acetate (x_1) + n -butanol (x_2)			
	A_0	A_1	A_2	σ
303 15	-0.022	-0.006	-0.004	0.00051
308 15	0.008	0.038	0.009	0.00050
313 15	0.010	0.064	0.057	0.00017
	Methyl acetate (x_1) + iso-butanol (x_2)			
303 15	-0.021	-0.013	-0.018	0.00052
308 15	0.006	0.039	0.012	0.00060
313 15	0.007	0.050	0.031	0.00016
	Ethyl acetate (x_1) + n -butanol (x_2)			
303 15	-0.024	-0.003	-0.004	0.00037
308 15	0.001	0.024	-0.003	0.00046
313 15	0.005	0.022	-0.005	0.00015
	Ethyl acetate (x_1) + iso-butanol (x_2)			
303 15	-0.023	-0.012	-0.013	0.00085
308 15	-0.002	0.012	-0.012	0.00068
313 15	-0.003	0.031	0.009	0.00017
	Propyl acetate (x_1) + n -butanol (x_2)			
303 15	-0.026	-0.004	-0.011	0.00049
308 15	-0.003	0.023	-0.005	0.00044
313 15	-0.007	0.015	-0.008	0.00015
	Propyl acetate (x_1) + iso-butanol (x_2)			
303 15	-0.029	-0.009	-0.013	0.00069
308 15	0.002	0.014	-0.022	0.00008
313 15	-0.008	0.015	-0.008	0.00003
	Butyl acetate (x_1) + n -butanol (x_2)			
303 15	-0.028	-0.008	-0.018	0.00047
308 15	-0.005	0.017	-0.013	0.00009
313 15	-0.004	0.016	-0.013	0.00002
	Butyl acetate (x_1) + iso-butanol (x_2)			
303 15	-0.032	-0.014	-0.016	0.00054
308 15	0.002	0.017	-0.013	0.00055
313 15	-0.004	0.002	-0.006	0.00061

Deviations with +/- sign are significant upto three digit of decimal in all the nine rules so studied. The system can be considered to be nearly ideal one for the test of various other mixing rules. The APD value for all the systems ranges from -0.3135 to 0.3612. Since liquids of different nature which has significant difference in molecular size

are considered, a particular relation provides excellent agreement at some places and deviates at others. The observed deviation are expected and can be ascribed to the volume additivity. As during mixing, excess volume is the measurement of molecular interaction in liquid mixtures. The structural property of liquid and liquid mixtures can be integrated through refractive indices employing molar refraction. Molar refractions for the selected binary mixtures of esters with alcohols are in the following order methyl acetate < ethyl acetate < propyl acetate < butyl acetate

Table 4. Average percentage deviation (APD)^a in the refractive index from different mixing relations for binary mixtures at various temperatures

Mixing rules	Methyl acetate (λ_1) + <i>n</i> -butanol (λ_2)		
	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K
A-B	0.1752	0.1147	0.2884
G-D	0.1752	0.1147	0.2884
L-L	0.1156	0.1198	0.2947
Eyk	0.1764	0.1165	0.2906
W	0.1155	0.0316	0.1834
H	0.1830	0.1257	0.3024
Nw	0.1714	0.1094	0.2817
O _s	0.1732	0.1120	0.2850
E-J	0.1771	0.1174	0.2918
	Methyl acetate (λ_1) + iso-butanol (λ_2)		
A-B	-0.0392	0.3521	0.0695
G-D	-0.0392	0.3521	0.0695
L-L	-0.0365	0.3562	0.0748
Eyk	-0.0383	0.3535	0.0714
W	-0.0826	0.2834	-0.0183
H	-0.0335	0.3612	0.0811
Nw	-0.0419	0.3477	0.0639
O _s	-0.0406	0.3499	0.0667
E-J	-0.0378	0.3543	0.0723
	Ethyl acetate (λ_1) + <i>n</i> -butanol (λ_2)		
A-B	-0.2636	-0.0139	-0.0348
G-D	-0.2636	-0.0139	-0.0348
L-L	-0.2606	-0.0108	-0.0310
Eyk	-0.2626	-0.0128	-0.0335
W	-0.3135	-0.0659	-0.0987
H	-0.2571	0.0023	-0.0264
Nw	-0.2667	-0.0171	-0.0387
O _s	-0.2652	-0.0156	-0.0368
E-I	-0.2621	-0.0122	-0.0328
	Ethyl acetate (λ_1) + iso-butanol (λ_2)		
A-B	0.2852	-0.0972	0.0541
G-D	0.2852	-0.0972	0.0541
L-L	0.2873	-0.0948	0.0571
Eyk	0.2859	-0.0964	0.0552
W	0.2503	-0.1379	0.0003
H	0.2898	-0.0919	0.0608
Nw	0.2831	-0.0997	0.0510
O _s	0.2841	-0.0984	0.0525
E-J	0.2863	-0.0959	0.0552

Table-4 (contd.)

	Propyl acetate (x_1) + <i>n</i> -butanol (x_2)		
A-B	-0.0271	-0.0445	-0.0907
G-D	-0.0271	-0.0445	-0.0907
L-L	-0.0259	-0.0433	-0.0890
Eyk	-0.0267	-0.0441	-0.0901
W	-0.0465	-0.0660	-0.1198
H	-0.0246	-0.0418	-0.0869
Nw	-0.0283	-0.0459	-0.0925
O _s	-0.0277	-0.0452	-0.0917
E-J	-0.0265	-0.0439	-0.0899
	Propyl acetate (x_1) + iso-butanol (x_2)		
A-B	0.1237	-0.0148	-0.0834
G-D	0.1237	-0.0148	-0.0834
L-L	0.1243	-0.0139	-0.0823
Eyk	0.1239	-0.0144	-0.0830
W	0.1132	-0.0290	-0.1037
H	0.1251	-0.0129	-0.0808
Nw	0.1231	-0.0156	-0.0847
O _s	0.1234	-0.0152	-0.0841
E-J	0.1240	-0.0143	-0.0828
	Butyl acetate (x_1) + <i>n</i> -butanol (x_2)		
A-B	-0.0475	-0.1035	-0.0916
G-D	-0.0475	-0.1035	-0.0916
L-L	-0.0471	-0.1033	-0.0912
Eyk	-0.0473	-0.1034	-0.0915
W	-0.0545	-0.1084	-0.0984
H	-0.0466	-0.1029	-0.0907
Nw	-0.0479	-0.1038	-0.0920
O _s	-0.0477	-0.1037	-0.0919
E-J	-0.0473	-0.1033	-0.0914
	Butyl acetate (x_1) + iso-butanol (x_2)		
A-B	-0.0317	0.0009	-0.0416
G-D	-0.0317	0.0009	-0.0416
L-L	-0.0316	0.0010	-0.0415
Eyk	-0.0317	0.0011	-0.0416
W	-0.0338	0.0007	-0.0445
H	-0.0314	0.0012	-0.0413
Nw	-0.0318	0.0008	-0.0418
O _s	-0.0318	0.0009	-0.0417
E-J	-0.0316	0.0008	-0.0415

$$^a 100 [(n_{\text{obsd}} - n_{\text{calc.d}})/n]$$

In general molar refraction increases with molecular weight for symmetric and asymmetric molecules. Density and refractive index depend on molecular weight and nature of solution. The effect of interaction between the two components become more and more predominant as the alkyl group of the normal esters increase in size due to their electron donating ability. Density and refractive index values decrease with increase of temperature from 303.15 K to 313.15 K.

For all the eight binary mixtures, Heller relation has exhibited deviation higher in value than Weiner, Newton and Oster relations at all temperatures.

It should be noted that the calculated average percent-

Fig. 1. Refractive index deviation n^E for methyl acetate (x_1) + *n*-butanol (x_2): (Δ) ethyl acetate (x_1) + *n*-butanol (x_2), (∇) propyl acetate (x_1) + *n*-butanol (x_2), ($\square$) butyl acetate (x_1) + *n*-butanol (x_2), ($\blacksquare$) at 303.15 K.

age deviations value between the Arago-Biot and Gladstone-Dale relations are exactly the same for all systems at all temperatures. This is expected because of similarities in the functional forms of these equations; as per literature²¹ Gladstone-Dale relation is more frequently used than the Arago-Biot equation. However, most generally, the Weiner relation gives the least deviation in n^E values as compared to other mixing rules.

Fig. 2. Refractive index deviation n^E for methyl acetate (x_1) + iso-butanol (x_2): ($\diamond$) ethyl acetate (x_1) + iso-butanol (x_2), ($\blacklozenge$) propyl acetate (x_1) + iso-butanol (x_2), ($\circ$) butyl acetate (x_1) + iso-butanol (x_2), ($\bullet$) at 303.15 K.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Their purity was checked as per the method given earlier²² and results agreed reasonably with corresponding literature values.

Mixtures were prepared by mixing the appropriate volumes of liquids in specially designed ground glass air tight ampoules and weighed in single pan balance (Mettler Toledo AB 204 electronic balance) to an accuracy of ± 0.0001 mg. Preferential evaporation losses of solvent from the mixture were kept to a minimum as evidenced by repeated measurements of physical properties over an interval of 2–3 days during which time no changes in physical properties were observed. The possible error in mole fraction is estimated to be around 0.0001. Density of pure liquids and their binary mixtures in the composition range of 0.0352 to 0.9565 mole fraction increments were measured by using pycnometer having bulb volume of 10 cm^3 and capillary with the internal diameter 1 cm^3 for each measurement: Sufficient time was allowed to attain thermal equilibrium in High Precision Water Bath, Cat No. MSW-274 thermostat, the bath temperature was monitored to ± 0.1 K with a calibrated thermometer. The reported density at 303.15 K, 308.15 K, 313.15 K are significant at four figures. An average of triplicate measurements was taken into account and their reproducibility was within range of $\pm 0.5\%$.

Refractive indices for the sodium *D* line were measured with a thermostated Abbe's Refractometer, SER No. 95033 with an error less than 0.0001 unit. These data were approximated to four digits of decimal. Water was circulated into the instrument through the thermostatically controlled bath. The refractometer was calibrated using glass test piece of known refractive index supplied with the instrument.

Conclusion :

All nine mixing rules could be successfully applied at lower concentration of esters omitting other factors such as volume reduction, volume addition and temperature. Heller equation could not give better results. All nine theoretical mixing rules performed well within the limits of experimental error. The deviation between theoretical and observed values of refractive indices for all systems taken under consideration can be reduced if the concept of excess molar volumes is taken into consideration. Results from Redlich-Kister polynomial equation reveal that strong intermolecular interactions related to decrease in molar volume and negative enthalpy change take place on mixing.

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